

Supplement to: Identifying climatic drivers of hybridization with a new ancestral niche
reconstruction method

SUPPLEMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Phylogenetic results—Within *Heuchera* sect. *Rhodoheuchera*, we recovered two novel relationships that were restricted to concatenation analysis (Fig. 2) and disagreed with previously published work, including concatenation approaches. First, *Heuchera bracteata* and *H. hallii* appear embedded within *Heuchera* sect. *Rhodoheuchera* rather than as a clade sister to *H. woodsiaephila* + *Heuchera* sect. *Rhodoheuchera* (as seen in the coalescent analysis [Fig. 3] and in Folk et al. 2017); all branches resolving this relationship have only moderate bootstrap support (<75%). Second, *Heuchera caespitosa*, resolved as embedded within *Heuchera* subsect. *Elegantes* in the coalescent analysis and in previous work (Folk et al. 2017, 2018b), had a different position as sister to *H. rubescens* var. *alpicola*, with these two taxa forming a clade sister and reciprocally monophyletic with respect to *H. bracteata* and *H. hallii*.

Two further results disagreed between concatenation and coalescent analyses but were already known to disagree among previous studies. The *Ozomelis* group, although only recovered with moderate support in our concatenated analysis (BS 71), was sister to all other species of tribe Heuchereae, congruent with results recovered previously using ribosomal ITS and ETS loci (Okuyama et al. 2008; Folk and Freudenstein 2014). Coalescent analyses instead recovered *Heuchera* as sister to the *Ozomelis* group with weak support (LPP 0.54) as seen in one of the analyses of Okuyama et al. (2012). Finally, *Heuchera glabra* was sister to the rest of the genus in the concatenation analysis, as seen in a previous total evidence analysis including morphology but not in DNA-only analyses (Folk and Freudenstein 2014), whereas in the coalescent analysis it was sister to a clade containing *H. maxima*, *H. micrantha*, and *H. pilosissima* (that is, *Heuchera* subsect. *Micranthae* sensu Folk 2015), in agreement with previous phylogenomic studies that included this species (Folk et al. 2017, 2018b). Otherwise,

relationships among and within genera other than *Heuchera* were highly congruent and largely well-supported across all methods. Several further relationships in the ASTRAL tree that did not receive high local posterior support were congruent with decisively supported nodes in the concatenation tree. Among taxa not included in previous nuclear-based phylogenomic studies, *Conimitella*, *Spuriomitella*, and additional species of *Asimitellaria*, *Heuchera*, *Lithophragma*, *Ozomelis*, and *Tiarella* were placed as expected based on previous studies (Okuyama et al. 2012; Kuzoff et al. 1999; Liu et al. 2020).

Chloroplast-nuclear phylogenetic discord was very similar to that found previously (Folk et al. 2017, 2018b), and overall simulation results were also similar, but our complete sampling of *Lithophragma* enabled the detection of a new putative chloroplast capture event, given that *Tolmiea* is nested within *Lithophragma* (Supplemental Figs. S2, S4). Both genera are morphologically well defined, and the latter has long been recovered as monophyletic and not closely related to *Tolmiea* with nuclear markers (Kuzoff et al. 1999; this work). This new topological placement is also unexpected under ILS alone (chloroplast clade frequency < 10e-9; best alternative relationship 0.047). We also corroborated the hypothesis of Okuyama et al. (2005) of two chloroplast capture events within *Asimitellaria* (Supplemental Figs. S2, S4).

Updated phylogenetic relationships—We have incorporated an updated generic classification for Heuchereae based on previous results (Folk et al. 2021). Greatly strengthened taxonomic sampling has confirmed previous results and provided additional support for the segregation of *Mitella* into multiple genera (*Mitella*, *Mitellastra*, *Pectiantia*, *Ozomelis*, *Spuriomitella*, *Asimitellaria*, *Brewerimitella*; Folk et al. 2021). While some relationships, such as the placement of *Heuchera* relative to the *Ozomelis* group, remain uncertain (Fig. 2), the

backbone of Heuchereae has largely been resolved. Relationships within genera typically receive decisive support and are consistent across analyses. Important exceptions are within *Heuchera*: *H. bracteata*, *H. hallii*, and *H. caespitosa* had unconventional placements in the concatenation analysis. Coalescent and concatenated analyses also differed in the position of *H. glabra*, whether as sister to all other species of *Heuchera* (concatenation, with weak support) or in a position close to *H. micrantha* (coalescence, with decisive support). Both of these placements have been seen previously in different locus sets on the same accessions (Folk and Freudenstein 2014; Folk et al. 2017). The inconsistency of placement for these taxa may represent two alternative placements in the gene tree set, resolved differently depending on analytical method and dataset, with the placement in coalescent analyses most consistent with previous work. The position of *H. glabra* and resolution within *Heuchera* sect. *Rhodoheuchera* have remained difficult despite repeated phylogenomic study, and a more focused study of these taxa is a prime target for future work in the group.

Hybrid detection—This work identified a new chloroplast capture event between *Lithophragma* and *Tolmiea* (Supplemental Fig. S4; Supplemental Table S3), genera of western North America that do not resemble each other morphologically and are not sister. While both genera contain polyploid species or populations, the entire *Tolmiea* clade is embedded within *Lithophragma*, suggesting the hybridization occurred in a diploid ancestor. This accords with the chromosome survey and phylogeny of Folk and Freudenstein (2014) focused on *Heuchera*, which showed that polyploidy was restricted to individual species or (more commonly) populations of species. There are no instances of fixed polyploidy in clades treated above the species level for the Heuchereae of North America, and most known cases of polyploidy do not

align with chloroplast capture events, suggesting autopolyploidy as the primary mechanism of polyploidization in Heuchereae and an unclear relationship (if any) to hybridization. The exceptions are three examples of allopolyploidy known so far: *Heuchera rubescens* var. *cuneata* (Folk et al. 2017), some populations of *Lithophragma bolanderi* (Kuzoff et al. 1999), and the Asian clade *Asimitellaria* (Okuyama et al. 2012).

SUPPLEMENTAL FIGURES

Fig. S1. Topology recovered under concatenation in RAxML using the 277 nuclear loci. Branch labels represent bootstrap percentages $\geq 50\%$. Branch lengths represent per-site substitutions. Informal clade names noted in the text are labeled with gray boxes. Outgroup branches (*Darmera*, *Rodgersia*, *Peltoboykinia*) are omitted for compact representation.

Fig. S2. Topology recovered in RAxML using near-complete chloroplast genomes. Branch labels represent bootstrap percentages $\geq 50\%$. Branch lengths represent per-site substitutions. Informal chloroplast clade names from Folk et al. (2017) are labeled with gray boxes. Outgroup branches (*Darmera*, *Rodgersia*, *Peltoboykinia*) are omitted for compact representation.

0.003

Chloroplast clade A

Chloroplast clade B

Chloroplast clade C

Fig. S3. Dating result for the nuclear phylogeny from MCMC_{TREE}. The *x*-axis represents time in millions of years; node bars represent 95% credibility intervals. Outgroup taxa are included here (cf. Figs. 2, 3).

Fig. S4. Dating result for the chloroplast phylogeny from MCMC_{TREE} using the 277 nuclear loci. The *x*-axis represents time in millions of years; node bars represent 95% credibility intervals. Red circles denote MRCA dates for chloroplast capture events inferred in Folk et al. (2017), as well as the event inferred here for *Tolmiea* (see Results). Outgroup taxa are included here (cf. Figs. 2, 3).

Fig. S5. Chloroplast clade frequencies expected given the nuclear gene tree distribution and ILS alone. These simulations used a nuclear scaling factor of 2. The scale represents chloroplast genome per-site substitutions.

Fig. S6. Chloroplast clade frequencies expected given the nuclear gene tree distribution and ILS alone. These simulations used a nuclear scaling factor of 4. The scale represents chloroplast genome per-site substitutions.

Fig. S7. MDS analysis, based on a Euclidean distance matrix between ancestral niche projection results for all 100 concatenated bootstrap trees and the concatenated best tree. Results are shown for two time periods, a warm (0.86 MYA) and cool period (0.46 MYA), selected from Main Text Fig. 3.

**MDS of Ancestral Projection Results
0.86 MYA (warm period)**

**MDS of Ancestral Projection Results
0.46 MYA (cold period)**

Fig. S8. Ancestral reconstructions across the 12 predictor variables on the ASTRAL topology. Given difficulties visualizing histogram data on trees, branches are colored by the bin with maximum probability density for each variable. Branch colors are on a spectrum from blue (low values) to red (high values), scaled to the minimum and maximum per variable. The original reconstructions and further plot data are at https://github.com/ryanafolk/heuchera_ancestral_niche/.

Fig. S9. Test of different bin numbers.

SUPPLEMENTAL TABLES

Table S1. Accessions included in this study.

Accession	Species	Source	Collector	Collector number	Voucher herbarium location	Locality
I23	<i>Asimitellaria acerina</i>	Newly sequenced	Okuyama	MA-MY1	Field collection	Yohoro, Maizuru City, Kyoto Pref., Japan
I114	<i>Asimitellaria amamiana</i>	Newly sequenced	Okuyama	MAM-02	Field collection	Sumiyo-cho, Amami city, Kagoshima pref., Japan
I116	<i>Asimitellaria doiana</i>	Newly sequenced	Umemoto	MD1501	Living accession, Tsukuba Botanical Garden	In the vicinity of Miyanoura river, Yakushima Isl. Kagoshima pref. Japan
I117	<i>Asimitellaria formosana</i>	Newly sequenced	Okuyama	MFO-LL31	Living accession, Tsukuba Botanical Garden	Lala-shan, Taoyuan Hsien, Taiwan
I39	<i>Asimitellaria furusei</i> var. <i>subramosa</i>	Folk et al. 2018a	Okuyama	MSU-Ko4	Living accession, Tsukuba Botanical Garden	Jorakuji, Koryo-cho, Shimane Pref., Japan
I37	<i>Asimitellaria japonica</i>	Newly sequenced	Okuyama	MJ-T5	Living accession, Tsukuba Botanical Garden	Takachiho-kyo, Takachiho-cho, Miyazaki Pref., Japan
I120	<i>Asimitellaria kiusiana</i>	Newly sequenced	Okuyama	MK-I16	Living accession, Tsukuba Botanical Garden	Oh-taki, Itsuki-mura, Kumamoto pref., Japan
I38	<i>Asimitellaria koshiensis</i>	Newly sequenced	Okuyama	MKO-M0901	Living accession, Tsukuba Botanical Garden	Igashima, Aga-cho, Niigata Pref., JAPAN
I121	<i>Asimitellaria kumaensis</i>	Newly sequenced	Okuyama	MY-I1302	Living accession,	Oh-taki, Itsuki-mura, Kumamoto pref., Japan

					Tsukuba Botanical Garden	
I36	<i>Asimitellaria pauciflora</i>	Folk et al. 2018a	Okuyama	MP-K1004	Living accession, Tsukuba Botanical Garden	Kibune-okumiya, Sakyo, Kyoto City, Kyoto Pref., Japan
I31	<i>Asimitellaria stylosa</i> var. <i>makinoi</i>	Newly sequenced	Okuyama	MSM-KKW2	Living accession, Tsukuba Botanical Garden	Kaikawa, Naka-cho, Tokushima Pref, Japan
I26	<i>Asimitellaria stylosa</i> var. <i>stylosa</i>	Folk et al. 2018a	Okuyama	MSS-KZ1106	Living accession, Tsukuba Botanical Garden	Kosaka, Ibigawa-cho, Gifu Pref., Japan
I119	<i>Asimitellaria yamatoensis</i>	Newly sequenced	Okuyama	MJ-A1107	Living accession, Tsukuba Botanical Garden	Akame 48 falls, Nabari city, Mie pref., Japan
I22	<i>Asimitellaria yoshinagae</i>	Newly sequenced	Sakaguchi	MY-KW1	Living accession, Tsukuba Botanical Garden	Naka-cho, Tokushima Pref., Japan
H148	<i>Bensoniella oregona</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	148	OS	FS Rd 23, near Bear Camp, Siskiyou Mts, OR, USA
I33	<i>Brewerimitella breweri</i>	Folk et al. 2018a	Okuyama	MB-RL9	Field collection	Rainy Lake Pass, Chelan Co., Washington, USA
I32	<i>Brewerimitella ovalis</i>	Folk et al. 2018a	Okuyama	MO-FC8	Living accession, Tsukuba Botanical Garden	Fletcher Canyon, Jefferson Co., Washington, USA
H109	<i>Conimitella williamsii</i>	Newly sequenced	Folk	109	OS	Hellroaring Trail, Spanish Creek Basin, MT, USA
I48	<i>Darmera peltata</i>	Newly sequenced	Folk	I-48	OS	Cultivated
I89	<i>Elmera racemosa</i>	Folk et al. 2018a	Soltis and Soltis	2179	WS	Kittitas Co., Washington, USA
H45	<i>Heuchera abramsii</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	45	OS	Mount Baldy, CA, USA

I74	<i>Heuchera acutifolia</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Matus	14560	TEX	Rancho Poza, VE, Mexico
H63	<i>Heuchera alba</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	63	OS	Along Hwy 55 3 mi W of Onego, WV, USA
H64	<i>Heuchera alba</i>	Folk et al. 2018b	Folk	64	OS	Pendleton County, WV, USA
I70	<i>Heuchera americana</i>	Folk et al. 2018b	Folk	I-70	OS	Polk County, TN, USA
H70	<i>Heuchera americana</i> <i>var. americana</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	70	OS	Berry Road, Wayne National Forest, OH, USA
H104	<i>Heuchera americana</i> × <i>H. pubescens</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	104	OS	Bank near Sandstone Falls, WV, USA
H59	<i>Heuchera americana</i> × <i>H. richardsonii</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	59	OS	Roadside woods off Hwy 19, Mark Twain NF, Shannon Co. MO, USA
H52	<i>Heuchera bracteata</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	52	OS	Dowdy Lake, CO, USA
H164	<i>Heuchera bracteata</i>	Newly sequenced	Folk	164	OS	Blair-Wallis road near campground, Medicine Bow National Forest, WY, USA
H37	<i>Heuchera</i> <i>brevistaminea</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	37	OS	Side trail near Pacific Crest Trail, Laguna Mts., CA, USA
H48	<i>Heuchera caespitosa</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	48	OS	Rose Lake Falls, CA, USA
H216	<i>Heuchera caroliniana</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	216	OS	Bank along Rocky Creek, intersection with Hwy 97, SC, USA
H138	<i>Heuchera chlorantha</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	138	OS	Along Hwy 35, OR, USA
H108	<i>Heuchera cylindrica</i> ("H. saxicola")	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	108	OS	Hellroaring Trail, Spanish Creek Basin, MT, USA
H112	<i>Heuchera cylindrica</i> ("H. saxicola")	Newly sequenced	Folk	112	OS	Galena Gulch road, just off Hwy 15, MT, USA
H140	<i>Heuchera cylindrica</i> <i>var. alpina</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	140	OS	Cliffs above Deschutes River, OR, USA
H159	<i>Heuchera cylindrica</i> <i>var. cylindrica</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	159	OS	Dry banks above Salmon River Road, ID, USA
I57	<i>Heuchera cylindrica</i> <i>var. glabella</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	I-57	OS	Fishtrap Lake, WA, USA
H35	<i>Heuchera</i> <i>eastwoodiae</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	35	OS	Small canyon along Senator Hwy, 3.6 mi S of Groom Creek, AZ, USA
H44	<i>Heuchera elegans</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	44	OS	Talus above road to Crystal Lake, 0.5 mi from Hwy 39, CA, USA
I46	<i>Heuchera glabra</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	I-46	OS	Cliffs along Glacier Highway near Juneau, AK, USA
I5	<i>Heuchera glomerulata</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	I-5	OS	Cliffs along Mule Creek Road, NM near AZ border, USA
H154	<i>Heuchera</i> <i>grossulariifolia</i> var. <i>grossulariifolia</i> 2x	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	154	OS	Cliffs above Shaw Mountain Road near Boise, ID, USA

H160	<i>Heuchera grossulariifolia</i> var. <i>grossulariifolia</i> 4x	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	160	OS	Cliff above roadside parking lot outside of Riggins, ID, USA
H56	<i>Heuchera hallii</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	56	OS	Along Rock Creek Hills Road, Lost Park, CO, USA
H39	<i>Heuchera hirsutissima</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	39	OS	Mount San Jacinto, CA, USA
H33	<i>Heuchera inconstans</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	33	OS	West Fork Creek Canyon, AZ, USA
I126	<i>Heuchera lakelae</i>	Newly sequenced	Hinton	18331	TEX	Sierra La Marta, Mpio. Arteaga, Coahuila, Mexico
I129	<i>Heuchera lakelae</i>	Newly sequenced	Villarreal	5471	TEX	El Coahuilón, Sierra de la Marta, Mpio. Arteaga, Coahuila, Mexico
L23-2	<i>Heuchera longiflora</i>	Folk et al. 2018b	Folk	L-23	OS	Pike County, KY, USA
FL-27	<i>Heuchera longiflora</i>	Folk et al. 2018b	Floden	s.n.	TENN	Talledega County, AL, USA
H65	<i>Heuchera longiflora</i> var. <i>longiflora</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	65	OS	Natural Bridge State Park, KY, USA
H98	<i>Heuchera longiflora</i> var. <i>longiflora</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	98	OS	Rocky bank, Hwy 209 ~5 mi N of Paint Rock, NC, USA
I21	<i>Heuchera longipetala</i> var. <i>longipetala</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	I-21	OS	Sierra de Tepoztlan, MO, Mexico
I6	<i>Heuchera maxima</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	I-6	OS	0.5 mi SE of Stanton Ranch, Santa Cruz Island, CA, USA
H150	<i>Heuchera merriamii</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	150	OS	Outcrops above Little Castle Lake, CA, USA
I51	<i>Heuchera mexicana</i> var. <i>mexicana</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	I-51	OS	Bufo del Diente, Sierra Chiquita, Tamaulipas, NL, Mexico
H134	<i>Heuchera micrantha</i> var. <i>diversifolia</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	134	OS	Dry cliffs along Hwy 542 near Excelsior Camp, WA, USA
H49	<i>Heuchera micrantha</i> var. <i>erubescens</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	49	OS	Roadside outcrops on Hwy 41, Inyo Co., CA, USA
H145	<i>Heuchera micrantha</i> var. <i>hartwegii</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	145	OS	Cliff along Hwy 101 (side of Humbug Mountain), OR, USA
H146	<i>Heuchera micrantha</i> var. <i>macropetala</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	146	OS	FS 2308 1 mi from Rd 23, Siskiyou Mts., OR, USA
H141	<i>Heuchera micrantha</i> var. <i>micrantha</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	141	OS	Viento State Park, OR, USA
I69	<i>Heuchera missouriensis</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	I-69	OS	Little Grand Canyon near Carbondale, IL, USA
H24	<i>Heuchera novomexicana</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	24	OS	Emory Pass Trail, NM, USA
H43	<i>Heuchera parishii</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	43	OS	Sugarloaf Mountain, CA, USA
H72	<i>Heuchera parviflora</i> var. <i>parviflora</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Fok	72	OS	Natural Bridge State Park, KY, USA

H50-1	<i>Heuchera parvifolia</i> ("H. duranii")	Newly sequenced	Folk	50	OS	McAfee Meadow, White Mountains, Mono County, CA, USA
H120	<i>Heuchera parvifolia</i> ("H. flabellifolia")	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	120	OS	Dry talus slope, Glacier Co., MT, USA
H53	<i>Heuchera parvifolia</i> var. <i>major</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	53	OS	Poudre Canyon Hwy, CO, USA
H55	<i>Heuchera parvifolia</i> var. <i>nivalis</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	55	OS	Along Rock Creek Hills Road, Lost Park, CO, USA
H165-2	<i>Heuchera parvifolia</i> var. <i>typica</i>	Newly sequenced	Folk	165	OS	Vedauwoo Glen road near Hwy 80, vicinity of campground, Medicine Bow National Forest, WY, USA
I56	<i>Heuchera parvifolia</i> var. <i>utahensis</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	I-56	OS	Cotterel Mountains., ID, USA
I55	<i>Heuchera parvifolia</i> var. <i>utahensis</i>	Newly sequenced	Folk	I-55	OS	Rock Butte NA, Wasatch National Forest, UT, USA
I59	<i>Heuchera pilosissima</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	I-59	OS	Marshall, Marin Co., CA, USA
H69	<i>Heuchera puberula</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	69	OS	Pea Vine Road near Big Springs, Ozark National Riverways, MO, USA
H96	<i>Heuchera pubescens</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	96	OS	Pilot Mountain State Park, NC, USA
H100	<i>Heuchera pubescens</i>	Folk et al. 2018b	Folk	100	OS	Floyd County, VA, USA
H20	<i>Heuchera pulchella</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	20	OS	Sandia Crest, NM, USA
H166	<i>Heuchera richardsonii</i> var. <i>grayana</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	166	OS	Roadside near Ledges State Park, IA, USA
I58	<i>Heuchera richardsonii</i> var. <i>richardsonii</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	I-58	OS	Wainwright, Alberta, Canada
I9	<i>Heuchera rosendahlia</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Gurney	s.n.	RSA	Basaseachic Falls, CH, Mexico
I43	<i>Heuchera rubescens</i> var. <i>alpicola</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	I-43	OS	Lone Pine Creek above Mirror Lake, Sierra Nevada Mts., CA, USA
I19	<i>Heuchera rubescens</i> var. <i>rubescens</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	I-19	OS	Monroe Canyon, E of Richfield, UT, USA
H26	<i>Heuchera rubescens</i> var. <i>versicolor</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	26	OS	Outcrop above Hwy 159, NM, USA
I4	<i>Heuchera sanguinea</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	I-4	OS	Middlemarch Pass, Dragoon Mts., AZ, USA
I85	<i>Heuchera soltisii</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	I-85	OS	Aguirre Springs, Organ Mts., NM, USA
H192	<i>Heuchera villosa</i> var. <i>arkansana</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	192	OS	Weddington Gap, AR, USA
H78	<i>Heuchera villosa</i> var. <i>intermedia</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	78	OS	Long Lick Road, Shawnee State Forest, OH, USA
I122	<i>Heuchera villosa</i> var. <i>macrorrhiza</i>	Newly sequenced	Floden	s.n.	Field collection	Big Bottom Road along the Cumberland River north of Cookeville, TN, USA

H90	<i>Heuchera villosa</i> var. <i>villosa</i>	Newly sequenced	Folk	90	OS	0.25 mi S of Lewis Fork Overlook on Blue Ridge Parkway, NC, USA
I1	<i>Heuchera villosa</i> var. <i>villosa</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	I-1	OS	Devil's Courthouse, NC, USA
I7	<i>Heuchera wellsiae</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Gentry	7198	RSA	Los Pucheros, Sierra Surotato, SI, Mexico
H23	<i>Heuchera woodsiaephila</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	23	OS	Scree slope, Capitan Peak, NM, USA
H22	<i>Heuchera wootonii</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	22	OS	Dry bank, Capitan Peak, NM, USA
rf523	<i>Lithophragma affine</i>	Newly sequenced	Thompson	9818	Field collection	UC Hastings Reserve, CA
rf516	<i>Lithophragma affine</i> ssp. <i>mixtum</i>	Newly sequenced	Thompson	6904	Field collection	Ranger Peak, CA
rf514	<i>Lithophragma bolanderi</i>	Newly sequenced	Thompson	4709	Field collection	Marble Falls Trail, Sequoia National Park, CA
rf519	<i>Lithophragma bolanderi</i>	Newly sequenced	Thompson	8127	Field collection	South Fork Merced River, CA
rf517	<i>Lithophragma campanulatum</i>	Newly sequenced	Thompson	7596	Field collection	Pit River, CA
rf513	<i>Lithophragma cymbalaria</i>	Newly sequenced	Thompson	1741	Field collection	Colson Canyon, CA
rf522	<i>Lithophragma glabrum</i>	Newly sequenced	Thompson	9292	Field collection	Washington Hill, CA
rf521	<i>Lithophragma glabrum</i>	Newly sequenced	Thompson	8438	Field collection	Klickitat River, WA
rf512	<i>Lithophragma heterophyllum</i>	Newly sequenced	Thompson	773	Field collection	UC Hastings Reserve, CA
rf518	<i>Lithophragma maximum</i>	Newly sequenced	Thompson	7735-1	Seed from Rancho Santa Ana Botanical Garden	San Clemente Island, CA
rf511	<i>Lithophragma parviflorum</i>	Newly sequenced	Thompson	s.n.	Field collection	Keating Ridge, ID
rf524	<i>Lithophragma tenellum</i>	Newly sequenced	Thompson	10516	Field collection	Buck Creek Overlook, CA
rf520	<i>Lithophragma thompsonii</i>	Newly sequenced	Thompson	8355	Field collection	Ephrata, WA
rf515	<i>Lithophragma trifoliatum</i>	Newly sequenced	Thompson	6794	Field collection	Hogsback Road, CA
H88	<i>Mitella diphylla</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	88	OS	Piatt Park, Munroe Co., OH, USA
I123	<i>Mitella nuda</i>	Newly sequenced	Garton	1171	NY	Bog east of Provincial Paper Mill, Port Arthur, Thunder Bay District, Ontario, Canada

I124	<i>Mitella nuda</i>	Newly sequenced	Boivin	12536	NY	A l'ouest du lac Iosegun, District de Jasper-Edson, Alberta, Canada
I125	<i>Mitella nuda</i>	Newly sequenced	Freudenstein	3040	OS	Iosco County, Michigan, USA
I35	<i>Mitella nuda</i>	Folk et al. 2018a	Okuyama	MN01	Living accession, Tsukuba Botanical Garden	Murii Trail, Engaru City, Hokkaido Pref., Japan
I25	<i>Mitellastrca caulescens</i>	Folk et al. 2018a	Okuyama	MC-FDR3	Field collection	Federation Forest State Park, King Co., Washington, USA
I130	<i>Ozomelis diversifolia</i>	Newly sequenced	Soltis and Soltis	2428	WS	Josephine County, Oregon, USA
H161	<i>Ozomelis stauropetala</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	161	OS	Roadside bank near Minnetonkia Cave, ID, USA
I118	<i>Ozomelis trifida</i>	Newly sequenced	Okuyama	MT1601	Living accession, Tsukuba Botanical Garden	Near Blewett Pass, Wenatchee Mountains, Chelan Co., WA, USA
H128	<i>Pectiantia pentandra</i>	Folk et al. 2017	Folk	128	OS	Pacific Crest Trail access from hwy 90, WA, USA
I49	<i>Peltoboykinia tellimoides</i>	Newly sequenced	Folk	I-49	OS	Cultivated
I50	<i>Rodgersia pinnata</i>	Newly sequenced	Folk	I-50	OS	Cultivated
I115	<i>Spuriomitella integripetala</i>	Newly sequenced	Okuyama	MI-AZW1205	Living accession, Tsukuba Botanical Garden	Hibara-wase-zawa, Kitashiobara-mura, Fukushima pref., Japan
H130:1	<i>Tellima grandiflora</i>	Newly sequenced	Folk	130	OS	Glacier Creek road, Mount Baker, WA, USA
H89	<i>Tiarella cordifolia</i>	Newly sequenced	Folk	89	OS	Hampton Hills Metropark, OH, USA
I113	<i>Tiarella polyphylla</i>	Newly sequenced	Okuyama	s.n.	Living accession, Tsukuba Botanical Garden	Hibara-wase-zawa, Kitashiobara-mura, Fukushima pref., Japan
H127	<i>Tiarella trifoliata</i>	Newly sequenced	Folk	127	OS	Pacific Crest Trail access from hwy 90, WA, USA
H131-C	<i>Tolmiea menziesii</i>	Newly sequenced	Folk	131	OS	Glacier Creek road, Mount Baker, WA, USA
H169:C	<i>Tomiea diplomenziesii</i>	Newly sequenced	Folk	169	OS	Small seep beside FS 23, Siskiyou National Forest, Josephine County, OR, USA

Table S2. Comparison of dating results based on nuclear concatenation, nuclear coalescent, and chloroplast data. Shown are dates for named clades only, with – indicating clades were not recovered for the analysis in question; dates are crown dates; units are MYA (millions of years ago). Bracketed values represent 95% credibility intervals.

Clade	Concatenated nuclear tree	ASTRAL nuclear tree	Chloroplast tree
<i>Asimitellaria</i>	4.98 [3.56, 6.11]	6.83 [5.70, 7.28]	6.42 [5.60, 7.59]
<i>Brewerimitella</i>	3.43 [0.7, 5.23]	3.89 [2.03, 5.89]	1.62 [0.9, 2.74]
<i>Heuchera</i>	9.19 [7.86, 10.22]	9.50 [8.87, 10.00]	–
<i>Heuchera</i> chloroplast clade A	–	–	4.00 [3.44, 4.66]
<i>Heuchera</i> chloroplast clade B	–	–	6.41 [5.63, 7.74]
<i>Heuchera</i> chloroplast clade C	–	–	3.17 [1.59, 7.49]
Heuchereae	11.99 [11.52, 13.12]	11.51 [11.30, 11.98]	10.20 [8.90, 13.23]
<i>Lithophragma</i>	4.90 [4.09, 5.75]	6.14 [5.45, 6.76]	–
<i>Mitella</i>	5.64 [4.04, 7.02]	5.86 [4.06, 7.31]	8.10 [6.37, 12.18]
<i>Ozomelis</i>	4.19 [2.95, 5.18]	3.71 [2.63, 4.86]	–
<i>Ozomelis</i> group	11.42 [10.94, 11.98]	10.85 [10.57, 11.19]	–
<i>Pectiantia</i> group	11.34 [10.84, 12.14]	10.34 [10.07, 10.61]	–
<i>Tiarella</i>	5.15 [3.89, 6.08]	5.51 [3.83, 7.34]	–
<i>Tolmiea</i>	4.48 [1.49, 6.40]	5.5 [3.14, 8.08]	3.6155 [0.7, 5.57]

Table S3. Summary of inferred chloroplast capture event clades and dates, reflective of Fig. 5. In the case of eastern species of *Heuchera* (subsects. *Heuchera* and *Villosae*), there is complex cytonuclear discordance at the population level. In the absence of sufficient population-level sampling, these have been marked as “unresolved.”

Putative donor	Putative recipient	Date (chloroplast analysis MRCA)	First report
MRCA(<i>Mitella</i>)	MRCA(<i>Heuchera caespitosa</i> , <i>H. elegans</i>)	3.17	Folk et al. 2017
MRCA(<i>Lithophragma heterophyllum</i> , <i>L. bolanderi</i>)	MRCA(<i>Tolmiea</i>)	3.62	This study
<i>Tiarella</i>	<i>Holochloa</i> group	4.00	Soltis et al. 1991 (but resolved differently here, with <i>T. cordifolia</i> treated below)
<i>Heuchera micrantha</i>	<i>H. wootonii</i>	2.86	Folk et al. 2017
<i>H. cylindrica</i> (population treated historically as “ <i>H. saxicola</i> ”)	<i>H. grossulariifolia</i> 4x	1.07	Folk et al. 2017 (sampled but unresolved in Soltis et al. 1991)
<i>H. cylindrica</i> (“ <i>H. saxicola</i> ”; different population from above)	<i>H. grossulariifolia</i> 2x	0.91	Folk et al. 2017 (sampled but unresolved in Soltis et al. 1991)
<i>H. cylindrica</i>	<i>H. parvifolia</i> (populations historically treated as “ <i>H. duranii</i> ”)	1.66	Folk et al. 2017
<i>H. cylindrica</i>	<i>Ozomelis</i>	2.59	Folk et al. 2017 (sampled but unresolved in Soltis et al. 1991)
<i>Ozomelis</i>	<i>H. micrantha</i> (northern populations treated as vars. <i>diversifolia</i> , <i>macropetala</i>)	1.39	Folk et al. 2017 (sampled but unresolved in Soltis et al. 1991)
<i>H. micrantha</i> var. <i>macropetala</i>	<i>H. parvifolia</i> var. <i>utahensis</i>	0.82	Folk et al. 2017
<i>H. micrantha</i>	<i>H. glabra</i>	0.31	Folk et al. 2017 (sampled but unresolved in Soltis et al. 1991)
Unresolved member of <i>Heuchera</i> subsect. <i>Villosae</i>	<i>Tiarella cordifolia</i>	1.38	Folk et al. 2017 (Sanger analysis)
Unresolved member of <i>Heuchera</i> subsect. <i>Villosae</i>	MRCA(<i>Heuchera</i> subsect. <i>Heuchera</i>)	1.72	Folk et al. 2017
Unresolved member of <i>Heuchera</i> subsect. <i>Villosae</i>	Unresolved members of <i>Heuchera</i> subsect. <i>Heuchera</i>	1.52	Folk et al. 2017
Unresolved member of <i>Heuchera</i> subsect. <i>Villosae</i>	Unresolved members of <i>Heuchera</i> subsect. <i>Heuchera</i>	0.82	Folk et al. 2017
MRCA(<i>Asimitellaria japonica</i> , <i>A. yoshinagae</i>)	<i>Asimitellaria yamotoensis</i>	2.31	Okuyama et al. 2005
<i>A. stylosa</i>	<i>A. acerina</i>	1.15	Okuyama et al. 2005

Table S4. Comparison of monophyly support among recent multilocus phylogenetic studies, focusing on named clades, with two additional major subclades for each of *Asimitellaria* and *Lithophragma*. “—” means the clade was not recovered; “X” means the sampling was not sufficient to test the presence of the clade.

Clade	This study, ASTRAL (LPP)	This study, concatenation (bootstrap)	Folk et al. 2018c	Folk et al. 2017, ASTRAL (multilocus bootstrap)	Folk et al. 2017, gene-partitioned concatenation (bootstrap)	Folk and Freudenstein 2014 total evidence, concatenated (ML bootstrap)	Okuyama et al. 2012, concatenated (bootstrap; subgenome A, subgenome B for <i>Asimitellaria</i>)
<i>Asimitellaria</i>	1	100	100	X	X	X	100
MRCA(<i>Asimitellaria formosana</i> , <i>A. japonica</i>)	1	100	X	X	X	X	99, 100
MRCA(<i>Asimitellaria stylosa</i> , <i>A. furusei</i>)	1	100	100	X	X	X	82, 100
<i>Brewerimitella</i>	1	100	100	X	X	X	100
<i>Heuchera</i>	1	100	100	100	100	100	100, 100
<i>Heuchera</i> sect. <i>Heuchera</i>	1	100	100	100	100	100	X
<i>Heuchera</i> sect. <i>Holochloa</i> (incl. <i>H. glabra</i>)	0.94	—	85	100	95	—	X
<i>Heuchera</i> sect. <i>Rhodoheuchera</i>	0.69	—	< 50	100	27	86	X
<i>Heuchera</i> subsect. <i>Cylindrica</i>	1	100	100	100	100	—	X
<i>Heuchera</i> subsect. <i>Elegantes</i>	0.9	—	71	98	—	—	X
<i>Heuchera</i> subsect. <i>Heuchera</i>	1	96	100	100	100	73	X

<i>Heuchera</i> subsect. <i>Micranthae</i>	1	100	100	100	100	100	100	X
<i>Heuchera</i> subsect. <i>Novomexicanae</i>	1	100	100	100	100	100	—	X
<i>Heuchera</i> subsect. <i>Villosae</i>	1	100	100	100	100	100	100	X
<i>Lithophragma</i>	1	100	X	X	X	X	X	X
MRCA(<i>Lithophragma</i> <i>heterophyllum</i> , <i>L.</i> <i>maximum</i>)	1	92	X	X	X	X	X	X
MRCA(<i>Lithophragma</i> <i>parviflorum</i> , <i>L. tenellum</i>)	1	92	X	X	X	X	X	99
<i>Mitella</i>								97
<i>Ozomelis</i>	1	100	X	X	X	X	X	X
<i>Ozomelis</i> group	1	100	100	X	X	52	90	
<i>Pectiantia</i> group	0.65	100	95	X	X	—	—	
<i>Tiarella</i>	1	100	X	X	X	X	100	
<i>Tolmiea</i>	1	1	100	X	X	X	X	X
Tribe Heuchereae	1	100	100	X	X	100	100	

Table S5. Comparison of ancestral niche reconstruction results between the new method and two previously developed methods. Results represent BIO1 (mean annual temperature), formatted as center/range. Centers report niche centroid as measured by each of these methods: max bin height (histogram method), maximum likelihood estimate (Phyloclim), and posterior median (Ambitus). Ranges report niche breadth as measured by each of these methods: range from min to max bin with at least 1% probability (histogram method) and 95% credibility interval max - min (Ambitus); note Phyloclim does not directly implement ancestral node estimates of niche breadth. Nodes reported represent the tribe and all non-monotypic genera.

Node	Histogram method	Phyloclim (Heibl 2011)	Ambitus (Folk et al. 2017)
MRCA (tribe <i>Heuchereae</i>)	9.844/18.564 °C	9.206 °C	7.453/9.252 °C
MRCA(genus <i>Heuchera</i>)	10.228/18.564 °C	8.942 °C	7.833/8.858 °C
MRCA(genus <i>Lithophragma</i>)	12.028/17.472 °C	11.56 °C	10.256/7.982 °C
MRCA(genus <i>Asimitellaria</i>)	12.028/13.114 °C	10.389 °C	11.238/6.867 °C
MRCA(genus <i>Mitella</i>)	7.66/21.84 °C	6.683 °C	5.793/11.227 °C
MRCA(genus <i>Brewerimitella</i>)	9.844/16.38 °C	5.999 °C	6.54/10.25 °C
MRCA(genus <i>Tiarella</i>)	5.476/18.564 °C	8.162 °C	7.563/11.339 °C
MRCA(genus <i>Ozomelis</i>)	6.568/15.288 °C	5.38 °C	5.076/10.252 °C